

1 ***In situ* real-time annealing of ultrathin vertical Fe nanowires**
2
3 **grown by focused electron beam induced deposition**
4
5

6 Javier Pablo-Navarro^{1,2}, Robert Winkler³, Georg Haberfehlner⁴, César Magén^{1,2,5},
7
8 Harald Plank^{3,4,6} and José María de Teresa^{1,2,5*}
9

10
11
12 ¹ Laboratorio de Microscopías Avanzadas (LMA) - Instituto de Nanociencia de Aragón
13 (INA), Universidad de Zaragoza, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain.

14 ² Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Aragón (ICMA), Universidad de Zaragoza-CSIC,
15 50009 Zaragoza, Spain.

16 ³ Christian Doppler Laboratory DEFINE, Institute of Electron Microscopy and
17 Nanoanalysis, Graz University of Technology, Steyrergasse 17, 8010 Graz, Austria.

18 ⁴ Institute of Electron Microscopy and Nanoanalysis, Graz University of Technology,
19 Steyrergasse 17, 8010 Graz, Austria.

20 ⁵ Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, Universidad de Zaragoza, 50009
21 Zaragoza, Spain.

22 ⁶ Graz Centre for Electron Microscopy, Steyrergasse 17, 8010 Graz, Austria.
23
24
25

26
27
28
29
30
31
32 E-mail address of each author:

33
34 Javier Pablo-Navarro (javierpablonavarro@gmail.com)

35 Robert Winkler (robert.winkler@felmi-zfe.at)

36 Georg Haberfehlner (georg.haberfehlner@felmi-zfe.at)

37 César Magén (cmagend@unizar.es)

38 Harald Plank (harald.plank@felmi-zfe.at)

39 José María de Teresa (deteresa@unizar.es)
40
41

42 *Author to whom correspondence should be addressed:
43
44

45 José María De Teresa (deteresa@unizar.es)

46 Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Aragón (ICMA)

47 Universidad de Zaragoza-CSIC

48 Facultad de Ciencias

49 Pedro Cerbuna 12. 50009 Zaragoza, Spain.

50 Tel: +34 876 553354

51 Fax: +34 976 761229
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Abstract

1
2 Focused Electron Beam Induced Deposition is a consolidated technique for the growth of
3
4 three-dimensional (3D) nanostructures. However, this single-step nanofabrication
5
6 method requires further efforts to optimize simultaneously dimensional and
7
8 compositional properties, in particular for deposits with a high aspect ratio. More
9
10 specifically, ferromagnetic 3D nanowires (NWs) with diameters in the sub-50 nm regime
11
12 and high metallic contents up to 95 at. % attract great interest to improve the final
13
14 performance of magnetic nanodevices such as magnetic tips for scanning probe
15
16 microscopy. In this work, we report on real-time monitoring during chemical purification
17
18 and structural crystallization processes of ultra-narrow 3D Fe NWs (<50 nm in diameter
19
20 achieved) by post-growth *in situ* annealing in a transmission electron microscope. NW
21
22 heating up to 700 °C in very high vacuum reveals the local increase of the metallic content
23
24 along the entire NW length concomitant with the growth of large Fe single crystals from
25
26 initially amorphous compounds. A metallic purity of 95 at. % is observed in several
27
28 regions, dramatically boosting the initial Fe content of 40 at. %. The real-time *in situ*
29
30 tracking of 3D nanostructures during thermal annealing is a key element to design and
31
32 optimize novel purification processes for the fabrication of customized components to be
33
34 integrated in spintronic, logic and sensing devices.
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 **Keywords:** focused electron beam induced deposition; iron nanowires; three-
49
50 dimensional nanostructures; composition purification; *in-situ* transmission electron
51
52 microscopy
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1. Introduction

The increasing demand for high-density and low-power data storage, combined with technology approaching quantum limits for downscaling, naturally entails the expansion from two-dimensional (2D) to three-dimensional (3D) architectures to reach ultrahigh density on information storage media. In the case of magnetism-based technologies, magnetic nanowires are the building blocks in the development of future 3D magnetic data storage devices [1]. The functionality of these nanostructures relies on the precise control of domain wall motions with spin polarized currents or magnetic fields in vertical nanowires, to boost the performance of these memories in terms of areal density and power consumption [2]. Focused Electron Beam Induced Deposition (FEBID) is a matured nanofabrication technique, which enables highly localized synthesis of functional nanostructures on almost any material and surface morphology. This direct-writing nanofabrication method has an unique status for the development of 2D [3] and 3D [4] objects with spatial resolution in the range of nanometers, without the need of masks, resists, etching- or lift-off processes [5]. The decomposition of a precursor gas adsorbed on the substrate surface by an accurately-directed electron beam enables the deposition of metallic [6], magnetic [7], insulating [8] and superconducting [9] materials only in the areas scanned by the beam. This outstanding versatility yields a broad spectrum of applications, covering circuit edit and mask repair [10], micro- and nano-contacting [11], photodetection [12], nano-sensing [13], magnetomechanical actuation systems [14], plasmonics [15], etc. However, the proper operation of such devices can be compromised when the functional properties of the nanostructures are not ideally tuned. One of FEBID main issues is the existence of chemical impurities due to incompletely-dissociated precursor molecules leading to incorporation of unwanted fragments inside the deposit, often containing carbon and oxygen. Purity improvement can be achieved by

1 precise control of primary electron beam parameters (beam energy and current), vacuum
2 chamber base pressure, precursor gas flux, substrate temperature, tilt angle of the gas
3 injection system, distance between the nozzle and the substrate, etc [16]. However, even
4 after optimizing these growth parameters, the purity of as-deposited structures often
5 remains moderate [17]. Thus, several strategies have been developed to enhance the
6 deposit purity: *in situ* [18] and *ex situ* [19][20] post-annealing treatments at high vacuum
7 and under controlled gas atmosphere [21], use of substrates at high temperatures during
8 growth [22][23], electron beam irradiation of the deposits [24][25], application of high
9 current densities [26] or use of carbon-free precursor gases [27] are the most widely-used.
10 Nearly all these approaches were performed for 2D deposits [28], whereas purification of
11 3D objects have been scarcely carried out [15][29]. Purification of 3D deposits present
12 specific problems: for instance, the architecture stability due the high-volume shrinkage
13 during heating treatments is critical [30].

14 FEBID of Fe [31], Co [32] and Ni [33] precursors gives rise to magnetic deposits in which
15 low metallic content leads to degraded magnetic properties. High purity 2D Fe and Co
16 deposits (~95 at. %) can be grown after optimizing the nanofabrication parameters
17 [34][35]. Nevertheless, in the case of 3D nanostructures with a high aspect ratio, as
18 relevant for vertical nanowires (NWs), the metallic content is drastically reduced for
19 decreasing diameter. Moreover, the natural oxidation of the surface upon air exposure
20 (typically 5 nm thick) becomes critical as the surface-to-volume ratio significantly
21 increases and impairs the ferromagnetic properties of the nanostructures due to the
22 formation of non-ferromagnetic species [36][37]. Therefore, novel strategies such as on-
23 purpose core-shell designs [38] or *ex situ* annealing treatments in high vacuum [29] have
24 been pursued to prevent and solve these issues.

1 While most annealing studies have been performed in post-process conditions (e.g. after
2 each temperature step), real-time evaluation concerning chemical composition, overall
3 morphology and local crystallinity is still rare, even though such studies would provide
4 deeper insight in their fundamental nature. Based on this motivation, we here use *in situ*
5 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) for studying the implications of thermal post-
6 growth annealing on Fe based FEBID NWs with atomic resolution [39]. The possibility
7 to analyze the results in real-time at each temperature step allows getting an insight on
8 the process dynamics, confining the required purification time scales. In more detail, we
9 focus on the formation and distribution of highly-pure metallic Fe phases, including their
10 crystallinity in real time (sample A). These results are compared with the *ex situ* annealing
11 experiments performed on specimens that initially showed a higher metal content
12 (samples B-F) (see Supporting Information). The two setups used for the growth in
13 different laboratories (Austria and Spain) led to different chemical composition of the as-
14 grown nanowires, allowing us to investigate the behavior of thermal post-processing of
15 3D magnetic NWs with a broader view. This improved understanding is the basis for
16 further optimization of magnetic NWs for future applications in sensing, memory and
17 logic.

42 **2. Experimental**

43 **2.1 Growth of 3D Fe NWs by FEBID.** Although FEBID 3D-nanoprinting allows the
44 fabrication of complex 3D designs [16], this study representatively uses a pillar geometry
45 for simplicity. The nanostructures (sample A; Austrian laboratory) were fabricated in a
46 commercial FEI Nova 200 dual beam microscope equipped with a thermal field emission
47 gun (FEG) electron column and a standard gas injection system (GIS) for depositing Fe
48 using $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$ precursor gas. The NWs were grown at room temperature on a heating
49 chip (Wildfire S3, DENSSolutions, The Netherlands) prepared to be loaded into a
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Wildfire TEM holder for subsequent *in situ* heating experiments.

Figure 1. (a) Heating chip mounted in the TEM holder with (b) an Fe-FEBID nanowire grown for real-time TEM annealing experiments. (c) Temperature profiles for the Fe-FEBID nanowire studied.

The chip substrate includes oval holes where the suspended nanostructures can be imaged, as shown in Figure 1(a-b). The chip was tilted during the vertical growth of the NW, so that the nanostructure projection falls into the hole once the chip recovers the horizontal position. After the optimization of the growth parameters, NWs of very small diameter (<50 nm), with a high aspect ratio (>30) and an initial moderately-low Fe relative composition (~40 at. %) were obtained. All deposits were fabricated using an electron beam voltage of 30 kV, electron beam current of 21 pA, growth pressure of 4×10^{-7} mbar (working pressure minus base pressure), precursor temperature of ~30 °C and a single spot exposure for 600 seconds.

2.2 Post-growth annealing in the Transmission Electron Microscope. The post-growth annealing in high vacuum was performed *in situ* in an FEI Titan Cube G2 60-300 using a Wildfire TEM holder from DENSSolutions (sample A). Figure 1(c) shows the temperature profile during the experiment, where individual annealing times are color-coded: 100 °C (12 min), 200 °C (12 min), 300 °C (12 min), 400 °C (56 min), 450 °C (36

1 min), 500 °C (44 min), 550 °C (14 min), 600 °C (47 min), 700 °C (26 min) and 800 °C (23
2 min).

3
4 **2.3 *In situ* Transmission Electron Microscopy characterization.** Scanning
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) imaging in combination with Electron
Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS) was performed using an FEI Titan Cube G2 60-300
equipment operated at 300 kV and fitted with a high brightness electron gun (X-FEG)
with monochromator and a Cs probe corrector (DCOR), which produces an electron probe
below 0.7 Å in STEM imaging, and a Gatan Imaging Filter (GIF) Quantum. The STEM-
EELS experiments were carried out with a 19.7 and 20.5 mrad convergence and collection
semiangles, respectively, an energy dispersion of 0.5 eV/pixel with a resolution of 1.5 eV
(FWHM of the zero-loss peak), a GIF aperture of 5 mm, a camera length of 58 mm, a
pixel time of 10 ms and an estimated beam current of 160 pA. Annular Dark Field (ADF)
images were acquired with a Gatan ADF detector in the GIF with an inner detector angle
of 38 mrad and an outer detector angle of 137 mrad.

3. Results

The nanofabrication of 3D Fe NWs with ~40 at. % metallic content and ~50 nm in
diameter was performed via FEBID. A live monitoring of the features during the
annealing allowed the *in situ* characterization of the structural and compositional
variations from 24 °C to 800 °C. This gave us the opportunity of choosing different
annealing times at each temperature depending on the changes observed or required.
Furthermore, the nanostructures can be tailored until the desired properties are achieved.
Based on this consideration, the sample was kept at certain temperatures as long as
significant variations were detected. Figure 2 shows a schematic illustration of the
dimensional and organizational modifications of the components depending on the
annealing temperature as obtained in the experiments. In brief, purified (~95 at. % Fe)

crystalline regions of the NW were obtained, reducing the lateral resolution down to ~30 nm in specific areas, but retaining the general shape of the nanostructure.

Figure 2. Sketch of the morphology, dimensions and composition distribution of an Fe-FEBID NW as a function of the annealing temperature as observed in the experiments. Fe, O and C are depicted in green, red and blue respectively.

ADF imaging and EELS compositional mapping in STEM mode have been used to trace the morphological, structural and chemical evolution of the NW with increasing annealing temperatures. Figure 3 illustrates the general features observed upon heating by focusing the attention on a central region of the NW. The average diameter tends to decrease as the temperature value raises, obtaining a 40 % reduction of the thickness in certain regions, dropping down from ~50 nm at 24 °C to ~30 nm at 700 °C. This is due to an expected volume shrinkage caused by the progressive reduction of carbon and oxygen content, due to the formation of volatile CO_x compounds as previously discussed [25][40]. Chemical analyses reveal that the NW core contains ~40 at. % Fe once they are exposed to air, before the annealing treatment. As shown in greater detail in Figure 4,

regarding the crystalline texture, the as-deposited NW has a nanocrystalline structure which begins to change in the early stages of the experiment.

Figure 3. ADF-STEM images of the central section of an as-deposited Fe-FEBID nanowire, sequentially annealed at 100, 200, 300, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600 and 700 °C. Yellow arrows are guides to the eye indicating the same point of the nanowire. The yellow dashed square in the image of the as-deposited nanowire indicates the area highlighted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. High-resolution ADF-STEM images of the area indicated with yellow dashed square in Figure 3 of an as-deposited Fe-FEBID nanowire, sequentially annealed at 100, 200, 300, 400, 450, 500 and 550 °C. Scale bars are 10 nm in all images.

From 24 °C to 300 °C, only minor structural changes are observed. At 100 °C crystallites up to ~10 nm begin to grow in specific regions, suggesting that a global homogeneous composition in the core is kept with the Fe starting to segregate from the rest of the components on specific areas. The low electron current density ($<40 \text{ nA/nm}^2$) concentrated on the nanowire ensures that the driving force of the crystal emergence is

1 provided by the heater temperature rise rather than by the irradiation-enhanced diffusion
2 phenomenon [41][42]. When the sample is heated to 200 °C, new isolated ordered
3 arrangements of atoms turn up, and oriented in different directions at several areas, whilst
4 maintaining the general structural shape of the NW. At 300 °C the number of high-purity
5 Fe nanocrystals increases inside the core, giving rise to an overlap amongst them. In
6 addition, general compositional changes happen, noticing a richer Fe central trace found
7 along the long axis of the nanostructure (see Figure 5). Raising the temperature up to 400
8 °C favours the clustering of the crystals, giving rise to an inhomogeneous distribution of
9 Fe, which produces areas with remarkable higher metallic content. Indeed, a particularly
10 active redistribution of the Fe, O and C can be noticed as a function of time, which is
11 illustrated in Figures 5. At 450 °C a grain size growth takes place with crystals spreading
12 all over the core thickness in certain regions.
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 5. STEM-EELS chemical maps of the central section of an as-deposited Fe-FEBID nanowire, sequentially annealed at 100, 200, 300, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600 and 700 °C, showing the spatial distribution of Fe, O, and C in green, red and blue, respectively. Yellow arrows are guides to the eye indicating the same point of the nanowire. Scale bars are 10 nm in all images.

Figure 4 shows a clear change in the NW microstructure, virtually removing most of the remained amorphous material in Fe-rich parts. It is also noteworthy that, since Fe-rich areas appear inside the NW, therefore C-rich and O-rich areas should appear in other areas. Moreover, given that the initial Fe content was low (~40 at. %), the complete purification throughout the whole nanostructure is not expected to occur whilst keeping the total volume constant, and similar behaviour was found in the 3D samples B-F with higher initial metallic content (≥ 75 at. %) (see Supporting Information). At 500 °C the diameter is not uniform anymore along the length of the nanostructure, considerably reducing its value below 45 nm in some sections. As illustrated in Figure 5, large Fe

1 grains grow in size, at the expense of surrounding smaller grains, to reach lateral sizes
2 close to the NW width. At 550 °C, the recrystallization of the Fe-rich regions is completed
3 and has produced the expected large crystals of α -Fe (bcc). This correlates very well with
4 the result obtained from samples B-F (see Supporting Information), and with the previous
5 observation of the transformation of amorphous Fe:C:O as-grown nanocomposites into
6 α -Fe single-crystals around this temperature [43]. In addition to that, when the component
7 distribution does not change anymore as a function of time at 550 °C, a temperature
8 increase to 600 °C is required to stimulate further compositional dynamics. Here, Fe
9 crystal migration in some areas of the NW is powerfully promoted, with the grain front
10 advancing with a mean speed of ~ 26 pm/s (see Video S1). For the sake of comparison,
11 iron carbon alloy nanoparticles were found to move inside a C nanopillar at 8 nm/s under
12 comparable temperatures [44]. In the case of 3D Fe-FEBID NWs, the diffusion suggests
13 being subject to the specific morphology of the regions, the available metallic sources
14 around the active grain front when they are still present and the possible crystal
15 accommodation within the NW. The NW segment represented in Figure 5 shows a
16 remarkable expansion of the Fe content along that section. However, despite not
17 displaying the whole length of the nanostructure to have a better assessment of the fine
18 compositional details, it is important to highlight that this local purification leads to the
19 accumulation of C and O in other regions of the NW as illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. At
20 700 °C, the NW reveals a final diameter of approximately 30 nm in the thinnest regions.
21 At this point, it is likely that the growth of large α -Fe crystals is halted as the supply of
22 small iron particles at close distances has stopped. The adopted configuration resembles
23 the one obtained for the previous temperature stage and it can be assumed that the
24 segregation between the components is finished. At 800 °C, the NW suddenly bends at
25 the upper part, suffering an important deformation and therefore losing the 3D pillar
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 original shape (see Figure S1). Hence, the large amount of C initially contained inside the
2 structure not only hampers obtaining a homogeneously purified structure, but also leads
3
4 to the collapse of the NW structure at high annealing temperatures. Besides, some Fe
5 clusters are observed moving around inside the more carbonaceous core areas whereas
6
7 the O almost disappears.
8
9

10
11 To obtain quantitative information about the Fe, O and C relative compositions, STEM-
12 EELS profiles were performed along the length (Figure 6) and the diameter (Figure 7) of
13
14 the NW at each annealing temperature. For the first one, the profiles were acquired
15
16 approximately in the same areas depicted in Figures 3 and 5 and by integrating over the
17
18 central ~12 nm. For the second one, the plots over the thickness of the nanostructure does
19
20 not provide fair information about the overall composition but allow studying the shell
21
22 composition and obtaining numerical values of the relative contents of Fe, O and C in
23
24 specific sections. In this case, since there is an active displacement of the components
25
26 depending on the temperature, we have selected the regions which illustrate the general
27
28 behaviour of the composition at the shell and the highest Fe percentage found throughout
29
30 the NW for each annealing temperature. Figure 6 indicates that the initial ~40 at. % Fe,
31
32 ~40 at. % O and ~20 at. % C is homogeneously distributed in the core from 24 °C to 300
33
34 °C. However, this calculation considers the contribution coming from the shell because
35
36 the whole thickness of the NW is integrated in the STEM-EELS data collection. As shown
37
38 in Figure 7(a-d), in this temperature range, a ~7 nm shell composed by ~10 at. % Fe, ~30
39
40 at. % O and ~60 at. % C represents nearly the 30 % of the total width. Thus, one can
41
42 assume that the real metallic content inside the core is much higher than the one displayed
43
44 for the total volume. Another relevant fact is the absence of the standard ~5 nm surface
45
46 oxidation layer which typically covers magnetic FEBID nanostructures with higher
47
48 metallic content [45]. This suggests the instantaneous formation of a C shell during the
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 growth of the original Fe NW, avoiding the natural oxidation process of the metal species
2 once the nanostructure is removed from the nanofabrication vacuum chamber. As a result,
3
4 the O signal decreases from the core to the shell. At 400 °C and 450 °C, a strong difference
5
6 in the Fe contents along the length has been detected. According to Figure 6(e-f), the
7
8 regions where a cluster of Fe appears improve the metallic composition up to the range
9
10 between 50-60 at. % at the maximum, as well as the O signal decreases down to ~20 at.
11
12 % . These data correlate appropriately with Figure 7(e-f). At 500 °C, the Fe relative
13
14 composition exceeds 60 at. % in the areas with the highest metallic content, where the O
15
16 is reduced below 20 at. %. At 550 °C, the Fe content in those regions increases to around
17
18 70 at. %. Simultaneously, the C content starts to decrease at the shell and percentages
19
20 below 50 at. % are obtained for the first time. At the same time, the O signal decreases
21
22 drastically in central regions. At 600 °C, looking at the transversal profile analysis shown
23
24 in Figure 7(i), the C signal varies the tendency and decreases dramatically down to zero
25
26 value in some sections. Consequently, the Fe is expanded all over the NW thickness, the
27
28 recrystallization and the local purification is accomplished locally, approaching almost
29
30 ~95 at. % with the O layer present at the shell.
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 6. STEM–EELS profiles as a function of the length of (a) an as-deposited Fe-FEBID nanowire and the same nanostructure sequentially annealed at (b) 100, (c) 200, (d) 300, (e) 400, (f) 450, (g) 500, (h) 550, (i) 600 and (j) 700 °C. The Fe, O and C compositions are represented in green, red and blue respectively.

Figure 7. STEM-EELS profiles of the relative composition of the highest-metallic areas as a function of the radius for (a) an as-deposited Fe-FEBID NW and the same nanostructure annealed at (b) 100, (c) 200, (d) 300, (e) 400, (f) 450, (g) 500, (h) 550, (i) 600 and (j) 700 °C.

1 Also, the Fe signal generally coincides with the O one in the external areas, which
2 demonstrates that metallic material is eventually oxidized. Adding this to the overall
3 sharp reduction of the diameter, the ferromagnetic diameter shrinks to ~25 nm. Finally,
4 at 700 °C no significant changes can be noted with respect to the previous temperature,
5 and further heating is not expected to bring any major improvements on the purity.
6
7
8
9
10

11 **4. Discussion**

12
13 In order to evaluate the degree of Fe purification with temperature, Figure 8(a) displays
14 the radial dependence of the average Fe composition found in the highest-metallic area
15 of the NW at each annealing temperature. These higher purification sections may vary
16 their location from one temperature to another. A clear increase of the highest Fe content
17 as a function of the temperature can be appreciated in Figure 8(b). Simultaneously, the
18 diameter evolution in these regions follows the opposite trend, decreasing down to 33 nm,
19 attaining a remarkable lateral resolution. Thus, sections of virtually pure Fe can be
20 obtained by means of this annealing treatment from a nanowire with low initial Fe
21 content, but the full metal purification along the nanowire is not achieved. The obtained
22 nanoscale phase segregation will entail non-homogeneous physical properties in the
23 nanowire, which will have a significant impact on the performance of nanodevices based
24 on this material. As shown in the Supplementary File, in Fe FEBID nanowires with higher
25 initial Fe content, the annealing process also promotes the phase segregation in areas with
26 higher and with lower Fe content. We can compare this behaviour with similar annealing
27 processes conducted in Co 3D NWs grown by FEBID using the $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ precursor,
28 which showed a complete purification and recrystallization of the nanowires at 600 °C
29 [46]. This indicates that a different mechanism is governing the purification process in
30 both nanomaterials, with profound implications on their functionality.
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 8. (a) STEM-EELS profiles of the average Fe relative composition as a function of the radius in the areas with the highest metallic content of the Fe-FEBID nanowire found at each temperature. (b) Maximum Fe relative composition (circle symbol) and average total diameter (square symbol) in the selected NW area shown in Figure 4 as a function of the annealing temperature.

In the case of applications requiring magnetic continuity, such as in magnetic domain-wall conduits [1], annealed Fe FEBID nanowires would not be appropriate. However, in the case of magnetic sensing devices such as Hall sensors, the use of a nanomaterial with purified magnetic areas surrounded by non-magnetic areas could be beneficial [47]. Such annealed Fe FEBID nanowires may also be of interest to magnetic tips used for Magnetic Force Microscopy for two reasons: the enhancement of the spatial resolution due to the

1 reduction of the nanowire diameter and the diminishment of their magnetic invasiveness,
2 currently needed in the measurement of magnetic skyrmions [48]. Another potential
3 application of annealed Fe FEBID nanostructures could be in the field of catalysis, given
4 that the small metallic nanoparticles formed could act as catalytical centres for the growth
5 of carbon nanotubes, as shown in the past with Co FEBID nanodots [49].
6
7
8
9
10
11

12 **5. Conclusions**

13 In summary, post-growth annealing treatment under high-vacuum conditions of ultrathin
14 3D ferromagnetic Fe nanowires (< 50 nm) fabricated by FEBID with the $\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_9$
15 precursor has been carried out. The morphological, compositional and crystallinity
16 changes as a function of the temperature and time have been monitored in real time inside
17 a transmission electron microscope, shedding light on the nanoscale processes involved
18 during the annealing process. According to the obtained results, annealing up to 700 °C
19 of an as-grown homogeneous nanocrystalline nanowire with an initial metallic content of
20 about 40 at. % Fe induces the coexistence of Fe-purified and crystallized regions in the
21 nanowire with other Fe-deficient amorphous regions. Thus, instead of the full metal
22 purification, this annealing method provokes a strong phase segregation in the nanowire.
23 Our work underlines the importance of in-situ studies with nanoscale resolution for the
24 optimization of nanomaterials, and the understanding of their functionality not in terms
25 of their average physical properties, but of the physical properties of their individual
26 constituents. Potential applications of these results in magnetic sensing and catalysis have
27 been discussed.
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Acknowledgements

1
2 Authors acknowledge financial support from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and
3 Competitiveness (MINECO) through the projects MAT2017-82970-C2-1-R and
4
5 MAT2017-82970-C2-2-R, and from the Aragon Regional Government (*Construyendo*
6
7 *Europa desde Aragón*) through project and E13_17R with European Social Fund funding.
8
9 J. P.-N. grant is funded by the *Ayuda para Contratos Predoctorales para la Formación*
10
11 *de Doctores* (BOE 12/06/15) of the Spanish MINECO with the participation of the
12
13 European Social Fund. The financial support by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Digital
14
15 and Economic Affairs and the National Foundation for Research, Technology and
16
17 Development is gratefully acknowledged. Financial support was also received from the
18
19 FFG Austria in the frame of the “Beyond Europe” initiative (Project AIM, Nr. 11056459).
20
21 This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and
22
23 innovation programme under grant agreement No. 823717 – ESTEEM3. Experimental
24
25 help by R. Krisper from the Institute of Electron Microscopy and Nanoanalysis is
26
27 acknowledged.
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37

References

- 38
39
40
41 [1] S.S.P. Parkin, M. Hayashi, L. Thomas, Magnetic domain-wall racetrack memory,
42
43 Science 320, (2008) 190–194.
44
45
46 [2] M. Vázquez, Magnetic nano- and microwires: design, synthesis, properties and
47
48 applications, first ed., Elsevier, 2015.
49
50
51 [3] E. Nikulina, O. Idigoras, P. Vavassori, A. Chuvilin, A. Berger, Magneto-optical
52
53 magnetometry of individual 30 nm cobalt nanowires grown by electron beam
54
55 induced deposition, Appl. Phys. Lett. 100 (2012) 142401.
56
57
58
59 [4] A. Fernández-Pacheco, L. Serrano-Ramón, J.M. Michalik, M.R. Ibarra, J.M. De
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- Teresa, L. O'Brien, D. Petit, J. Lee, R.P. Cowburn, Three dimensional magnetic nanowires grown by focused electron-beam induced deposition, *Sci. Rep.* 3 (2013) 1492.
- [5] I. Utke, P. Hoffmann, J. Melngailis, Gas-assisted focused electron beam and ion beam processing and fabrication, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 26 (2008) 1197–1276.
- [6] D.N. Madsen, K. Mølhave, R. Mateiu, A.M. Rasmussen, M. Brorson, C.J.H. Jacobsen, P. Bøggild, Soldering of nanotubes onto microelectrodes, *Nano Lett.* 3 (2003) 47–49.
- [7] G.C. Gazzadi, J.J.L. Mulders, P. Trompenaars, A. Ghirri, A. Rota, M. Affronte, S. Frabboni, Characterization of a new cobalt precursor for focused beam deposition of magnetic nanostructures, *Microelectron. Eng.* 88 (2011) 1955–1958.
- [8] S. Lipp, L. Frey, C. Lehrer, B. Frank, E. Demm, S. Pauthner, H. Ryssel, Tetramethoxysilane as a precursor for focused ion beam and electron beam assisted insulator (SiO_x) deposition, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 14 (1996) 3920–3923.
- [9] J. Barzola-Quiquia, S. Dusari, C. Chilotte, P. Esquinazi, Andreev reflection and granular superconductivity features observed in mesoscopic samples using amorphous tungsten carbide superconductors, *J. Supercond. Nov. Magn.* 24 (2011) 463–469.
- [10] T. Liang, E. Frenberg, B. Lieberman, A. Stivers, Advanced photolithographic mask repair using electron beams, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 23 (2005) 3101–3105.
- [11] N. Sharma, P. Vugts, C. Daniels, W. Keuning, J.T. Kohlhepp, O. Kurnosikov, B.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- Koopmans, Multi-channel Andreev reflection in Co-W nanocontacts fabricated using focused electron/ion beam induced deposition, *Nanotechnology*, 25 (2014) 495201.
- [12] K. Makise, K. Mitsuishi, M. Shimojo, K. Furuya, A nanosized photodetector fabricated by electron-beam-induced deposition, *Nanotechnology* 20 (2009) 2–6.
- [13] M. Moczala, K. Kwoka, T. Piasecki, P. Kunicki, A. Sierakowski, T. Gotszalk, Fabrication and characterization of micromechanical bridges with strain sensors deposited using focused electron beam induced technology, *Microelectron. Eng.* 176 (2017) 111–115.
- [14] P. Vavassori, M. Pancaldi, M. J. Perez-Roldan, A. Chuvilin, A. Berger, Remote magnetomechanical nanoactuation, *Small* 12 (2016) 1013–1023.
- [15] R. Winkler, F.-P. Schmidt, U. Haselmann, J.D. Fowlkes, B.B. Lewis, G. Kothleitner, P.D. Rack, H. Plank, Direct-write 3D nanoprinting of plasmonic structures, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 9 (2017) 8233–8240.
- [16] R. Winkler, B.B. Lewis, J.D. Fowlkes, H. Plank, P.D. Rack, High-fidelity 3D-nanoprinting via focused electron beams: growth fundamentals, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 1 (2018) 1014–1027.
- [17] T. Bret, I. Utke, A. Bachmann, and P. Hoffmann, In situ control of the focused-electron-beam-induced deposition process, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 83 (2003) 4005–4007.
- [18] M.V. Puydinger Dos Santos, M.F. Velo, R.D. Domingos, Y. Zhang, X. Maeder, C. Guerra-Nuñez, J.P. Best, F.Béron, K.R. Pirota, S. Moshkalev, J.A. Diniz, I. Utke, Annealing-based electrical tuning of cobalt-carbon deposits grown by

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

focused-electron-beam-induced deposition, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 8
(2016) 32496–32503.

- [19] K. Mitsuishi, M. Shimojo, M. Tanaka, M. Takeguchi, K. Furuya, Resolution in new nanofabrication technique combining electron-beam-induced deposition and low-energy ion milling, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* 44 (2005) 5627–5630.
- [20] M. Shimojo, M. Takeguchi, M. Tanaka, K. Mitsuishi, K. Furuya, Electron beam-induced deposition using iron carbonyl and the effects of heat treatment on nanostructure, *Appl. Phys. A* 79 (2004), 1869–1872.
- [21] D. Belić, M.M. Shawrav, M. Gavagnin, M. Stöger-Pollach, H.D. Wanzenboeck, E. Bertagnolli, Direct-write deposition and focused-electron-beam-induced purification of gold nanostructures, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7 (2015) 2467–2479.
- [22] R. Córdoba, J. Sesé, J.M. De Teresa, M.R. Ibarra, Microelectronic engineering high-purity cobalt nanostructures grown by focused-electron-beam-induced deposition at low current, *Microelectron. Eng.* 87 (2010) 1550–1553.
- [23] J.J.L. Mulders, L.M. Belova, A. Riazanova, Electron beam induced deposition at elevated temperatures: compositional changes and purity improvement, *Nanotechnology* 22 (2011) 055302.
- [24] H. Plank, J.H. Noh, J.D. Fowlkes, K. Lester, B.B. Lewis, and P.D. Rack, Electron-beam-assisted oxygen purification at low temperatures for electron-beam-induced Pt deposits: towards pure and high-fidelity nanostructures, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 6 (2014) 1018–1024.
- [25] B. Geier, C. Gspan, R. Winkler, R. Schmied, J.D. Fowlkes, H. Fitzek, S. Rauch,

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- J. Rattenberger, P.D. Rack, H. Plank, Rapid and highly compact purification for focused electron beam induced deposits: a low temperature approach using electron stimulated H₂O reactions, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118 (2014) 14009–14016.
- [26] G.C. Gazzadi, S. Frabboni, Structural transitions in electron beam deposited Co-carbonyl suspended nanowires at high electrical current densities, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 6 (2015) 1298–1305.
- [27] K.L. Klein, S.J. Randolph, J.D. Fowlkes, L.F. Allard, H.M. Meyer, M.L. Simpson, P.D. Rack, Single-crystal nanowires grown via electron-beam-induced deposition, *Nanotechnology* 19 (2008) 345705.
- [28] A. Botman, J.J.L. Mulders, C.W. Hagen, Creating pure nanostructures from electron-beam-induced deposition using purification techniques: a technology perspective, *Nanotechnology* 20 (2009) 372001.
- [29] J. Pablo-Navarro, C. Magén, J.M. De Teresa, Purified and crystalline three-dimensional electron-beam-induced deposits: the successful case of cobalt for high-performance magnetic nanowires, *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 1 (2018) 38–42.
- [30] M.V. Puydinger dos Santos, A. Szkudlarek, A. Rydosz, C. Guerra-Nuñez, F. Béron, K.R. Pirota, S. Moshkalev, J.A. Diniz, I. Utke, Comparative study of post-growth annealing of Cu(hfac)₂, Co₂(CO)₈ and Me₂Au(acac) metal precursors deposited by FEBID, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 9 (2018) 91–101.
- [31] R.R. Kunz, T.M. Mayer, Catalytic growth rate enhancement of electron beam deposited iron films, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 50 (1987) 962–964.
- [32] Y.M. Lau, P.C. Chee, J.T.L. Thong, V. Ng, Properties and applications of cobalt-based material produced by electron-beam-induced deposition, *J. Vac. Sci.*

Technol. A 20 (2002) 1295–1302.

- 1
2
3 [33] A. Perentes, G. Sinicco, G. Boero, B. Dwir, P. Hoffmann, Focused electron beam
4 induced deposition of nickel, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 25 (2007) 2228–2232.
5
6
7
8
9 [34] T. Lukasczyk, M. Schirmer, H.-P. Steinrück, H. Marbach, Electron-beam-
10 induced deposition in ultrahigh vacuum: lithographic fabrication of clean iron
11 nanostructures, *Small* 4 (2008) 841–846.
12
13
14
15
16 [35] A. Fernández-Pacheco, J.M. De Teresa, R. Córdoba, M.R. Ibarra,
17 Magnetotransport properties of high-quality cobalt nanowires grown by focused-
18 electron-beam-induced deposition, *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.* 42 (2009) 055005.
19
20
21
22
23
24 [36] L.A. Rodríguez, L. Deen, R. Córdoba, C. Magén, E. Snoeck, B. Koopmans, J.M.
25 De Teresa, Influence of the shape and surface oxidation in the magnetization
26 reversal of thin iron nanowires grown by focused electron beam induced
27 deposition, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 6 (2015) 1319–1331.
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35 [37] S. Sangiao, C. Magén, D. Mofakhami, G. De Loubens, J.M. De Teresa, Magnetic
36 properties of optimized cobalt nanospheres grown by focused electron beam
37 induced deposition (FEBID) on cantilever tips, *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 8 (2017)
38 2106–2115.
39
40
41
42
43
44
45 [38] J. Pablo-Navarro, C. Magén, J.M. De Teresa, Three-dimensional core–shell
46 ferromagnetic nanowires grown by focused electron beam induced deposition,
47 *Nanotechnology* 27 (2016) 285302.
48
49
50
51
52
53 [39] R. Straubinger, A. Beyer, T. Ochs, W. Stolz, K. Volz, In situ thermal annealing
54 transmission electron microscopy (TEM) investigation of III/V semiconductor
55 heterostructures using a setup for safe usage of toxic and pyrophoric gases,
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Microsc. Microanal. 23 (2017) 751–757.

- 1
2
3 [40] R. Córdoba, R. Fernández-Pacheco, A. Fernández-Pacheco, A. Gloter, C. Magén,
4
5 O. Stéphan, M.R. Ibarra, J.M. De Teresa, Nanoscale chemical and structural
6
7 study of Co-based FEBID structures by STEM-EELS and HRTEM, *Nanoscale*
8
9 *Res. Lett.* 6 (2011) 592.
10
11
12
13 [41] B. Liu, T. Tahmasebi, K. Ong, H. Teo, Z. Mo, J. Lam, P.K. Tan, Y. Zhao, Z.
14
15 Dong, D. Houssameddine, J. Wang, J. Xue, Z. Mai, Electron radiation-induced
16
17 material diffusion and nanocrystallization in nanostructured amorphous CoFeB
18
19 thin film” *Acta Mater.* 161 (2018) 221–236.
20
21
22
23 [42] S. Frabboni, G.C. Gazzadi, L. Felisari, A. Spessot, Fabrication by electron beam
24
25 induced deposition and transmission electron microscopic characterization of
26
27 sub-10-nm freestanding Pt nanowires, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 88 (2006) 213116.
28
29
30
31 [43] M. Takeguchi, M. Shimojo, K. Furuya, Fabrication of magnetic nanostructures
32
33 using electron beam induced chemical vapour deposition, *Nanotechnology* 16
34
35 (2005) 1321–1325.
36
37
38
39 [44] T. Ichihashi, J. Fujita, M. Ishida, Y. Ochiai, In situ observation of carbon-
40
41 nanopillar tubulization caused by liquidlike iron particles, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 92
42
43 (2004) 215702.
44
45
46
47 [45] J. Nogués, J. Sort, V. Langlais, V. Skumryev, S. Suriñach, J.S. Muñoz, M.D.
48
49 Baró, Exchange bias in nanostructures, *Phys. Rep.* 422 (2005) 65–117.
50
51
52
53 [46] M.J. Martínez-Pérez, J. Pablo-Navarro, B. Müller, R. Kleiner, C. Magén, D.
54
55 Koelle, J.M. De Teresa, J. Sesé, NanoSQUID magnetometry on individual as-
56
57 grown and annealed Co nanowires at variable temperature, *Nano Lett.* 18 (2018)
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

7674–7682.

- 1
2
3 [47] M. Gabureac, L. Bernau, I. Utke, G. Boero, Granular Co-C nano-Hall sensors by
4 focused-beam-induced deposition, *Nanotechnology* 21 (2010) 115503.
5
6
7
8
9 [48] E. Berganza, M. Jaafar, M. Goiriena-Goikoetxea, J. Pablo-Navarro, A. García-
10 Arribas, K. Gusliyenکو, C. Magén, J.M. De Teresa, O. Chubykalo-Fesenکو, A.
11 Asenjo, Observation of hedgehog skyrmions in sub-100 nm soft magnetic
12 nanodots, arXiv: 1803.08768.
13
14
15
16
17
18
19 [49] M.H. Ervin, B.M. Nichols, Electron beam induced deposition of cobalt for use as
20 single- and multiwalled carbon nanotube growth catalyst, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B*
21 27 (2009) 2982–2985.
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Supplementary Material

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: SI_Manuscript_LAST.pdf](#)

Video Still

[Click here to download Video Still: VideoS1.avi](#)